

A Systematic Review on the State of Special Education in the Philippines: Identifying Challenges, Gaps, and Future Directions

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ABSTRACT

This study is a systematic review of the state of special education in the Philippines with sharp focus on the challenges, research gaps, and future research directions. Driven by the lack of a systematic inventory of local studies that capture challenges in the implementation of special education, this paper looked into pertinent studies from research repositories and academic search engines such as Elsevier, ERIC, Philippine e-journal, Google Scholar, and Virtual LRC. Of the 362 studies that showed up in the initial search, 42 studies were included for review after undergoing two stages of rigorous screening based on the eligibility criteria set and consistent with the processes prescribed in the PRISMA Expanded Checklist 2020. The review revealed challenges on instruction, diverse learning environments, curriculum development, stakeholders' engagement, and training and professional development. The researcher identified gaps such as lack of discourse on the dimension of assessment and reporting, limited number of studies dedicated towards curriculum development and diverse learning environment, thin set of literature on SPED teaching preparation of general education teachers, absence of evaluation studies on parental and family SPED trainings, and the methodological gap of limited qualitative evaluation studies in special education. The identified gaps serve as basis for future research undertakings towards enriching discourse on special education and improving practices for social inclusion of learners with special education needs in the Philippines.

Keywords: Inclusive Education; Special Education; Systematic Review; Challenges; SPED learners

INTRODUCTION

Several laws have already been put in place to ensure that special learners are not denied of their right to education and are able to live with dignity and in full. This is both an international obligation and a constitutional mandate as expressed under Article 26 of the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights as well as Article 14 Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution. Enabling these mandates are special laws that have been promulgated such as Republic Act No. 7277 (Magna Carta for Disabled Persons) and Republic Act No. 11650 (Inclusion and Services for Learners with Disabilities in Support of Inclusive Education), all designed to ensure equitable access to quality education (Gita-Carlos, 2022).

The actualization of these laws is also noticeably embedded in the country's education policy-making. Department of Education (DepED) Order 11, s. 2000, for instance, built the mandate for each school division to have at least one special education center. Department Order No. 6, s. 2006 meanwhile compelled secondary schools to also offer SPED program. The highlight on inclusive education was even more pronounced in the enactment of the K to 12 Basic Education Program in 2013 which, as DepEd declared, was founded on the core principle of inclusive education (DepEd, 2020). Several operational guidelines have been made thereafter, including DepEd Order No. 38, s. 2015 which covered guidelines on the utilization of SPED funds (Ajoc, 2019).

In all these legal instrumentalities, it must be noted that the ultimate goal of special education is the inclusion of children with special needs into the regular school system and eventually in the community (DepEd, 2020). Hence, learners with special education needs have found themselves not only in special education centers but even in the congested classrooms of Philippine public schools. They share seats with regular learners and are taught by general education teachers who lack specialization on the field of special education.

However, the well-meaning intention of systematic and deepening inclusion of students with exceptionalities into the mainstream come at the heels of the lack of special education centers and teachers in the Philippine public education system. In a report by Sales (2019), there are only 648 special education centers and ordinary schools which are offering inclusive education, with 471 catering to elementary students and 177 to high school students. The DepEd has also reported 2,601 SPED teachers in elementary and 284 in the secondary levels (Hernando-Halipot, 2019). Due to these infrastructural and workforce deficiencies, mainstreaming special learners surfaces as just one of the many challenges confronted not only by the learners, their parents and their teachers, but the broader discipline of education management. Various other studies have brought up issues on curriculum, instruction, insufficient teachers' training among other dimensions.

The researcher—herself a school principal of a public elementary school which integrates special learners to mainstream classes—has witnessed firsthand the difficulties surrounding special education in mainstream classes. These difficulties are also laid bare in empirical studies but have yet to be collated in order to comprehensively track where we are right now in the production of knowledge, identify research gaps, and identify areas that need further attention in research. The lack of a consolidated account of the inclusive education challenges faced by education managers in the Philippines like herself prompted the thematic focus of this review.

The researcher, thus, engaged in the substantive task of systematically providing an inventory of relevant studies that concern particularly with inclusive education catering to

learners with special education needs in the basic education context of the Philippines. Through a rigorous search from research databases and search engines, this paper hopes to identify and synthesize education challenges as contributed by various empirical illustrations in the country in order to sharpen situational understanding of special education needs thereby guiding both research and policy directions

Research Questions

- (1) What are the challenges related to inclusive education, particularly catering to learners with special education needs, in the Philippine context?
- (2) What are the gaps in research?
- (3) What recommendations can be drawn in this survey of literature?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the methods that the researcher has undertaken to conduct the review process of this systematic review. The structure of this section was guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) 2020 Expanded Checklist (Page et al., 2021) to ensure adherence to standard practice of reporting systematic reviews.

Eligibility Criteria. In selecting the studies included in this paper, the researcher used the following inclusion criteria: (1) studies conducted in the Philippines; (2) studies conducted in public elementary and high schools or special education center; (3) studies focusing on inclusive education or special education; and (4) studies published from 2013 and beyond. Conversely, studies were excluded if they: (1) were not conducted in the Philippines; (2) locale is not public elementary or high school; (3) did not focus on inclusive or special education; (5) studies published before 2013; and (6) are duplicate copies of the same study.

By “studies,” the researcher meant any published study available online including, but not limited to academic journal articles, conference abstracts, and book chapters. The researcher considered all research designs that contributed in addressing the research questions raised in the study—whether quantitative, qualitative or mixed—to ensure a comprehensive understanding of special education in the country. Moreover, the researcher purposively identified 2013 as a starting point for the reference criterion as it has been noted in literature that inclusive and special education in the Philippine education has taken significant stride after the enactment of the K-12 curriculum in 2013.

Information Sources. The researcher searched through digital repositories such as Scopus (www.elsevier.com), Education Resources Information Center (www.eric.ed.gov) and Philippine e-journals (www.ejournals.ph) as well as from academic search engines such as Google Scholar (www.scholar.google.com) and Virtual Learning Resource Center (www.virtuallrc.com). These databases were shortlisted as they subscribe to a wide range of journals that contain writings on education.

Search Strategy. The researcher initially conducted a general Google search to gloss over references that could potentially help inform the study as well as to get the maximum possible number of literatures. As Higgins et al. (2019) put it, a broad search strategy is designed to maximize the level of sensitivity to identify potential studies. After looking through the general

picture, the researcher narrowed down searches using the Boolean operators (OR & AND) to combine various components of the keywords to look for resources in the electronic databases mentioned above. The keywords include: “special education Philippines,” “inclusive education Philippines,” “sped classes Philippines,” among others.

Selection Process. A total of 42 studies were included in this review. The study selection process consisted of two stages: title/abstract screening and full-text screening. The researcher first looked into the title and read through the abstract to screen whether the variables involved in the resources were of any significance to the research at hand. The eligibility criteria used in the earlier section was used as a standard in finalizing the studies that were included in this systematic review.

Table 1. *Study Selection*

Database/Search Engine	Records Identified	Records Screened	Studies included in the review
Google Scholar	150	36	23
ERIC	78	12	3
Scopus (Elsevier)	0	0	0
Philippine e-journals	79	27	12
Virtual LRC	55	9	4
Total	362	84	42

Data Collection Process. After systematically selecting the studies reviewed, they were grouped based on the themes that emerged in the search particularly: curriculum development, training and professional development, stakeholders’ engagement, diverse learning environment, and instruction. The researcher developed a data extraction form to systematically extract relevant information from the studies selected based on themes, reference components, and research design.

Synthesis Methods. The findings from the included studies were synthesized considering the identified themes and research objectives. The researcher opted to write the results both in narrative format and tabular structure to display the results of individual studies and syntheses.

RESULTS DISCUSSION

After rigorous review and analysis of existing literature, nine constructs in the realm of special education have emerged: instruction (14), diverse learning environment (9), curriculum development (4 studies), stakeholders’ engagement (8), training and professional development (7), In terms of methodology used, the most used research design is quantitative methods (22), followed by qualitative (11), mixed methods approach (7), review (scoping-1, document review-1).

Table 2. *Survey of Literature*

Category	Reference	Research Design
	Mangonon (2022)	Quantitative
	Roxas et al. (2019)	Quantitative

Curriculum development	Raguindin (2020)	Qualitative
	Pawilen et al. (2018)	Qualitative
	Alfane (2020)	Quantitative
Training and Professional Development	Aranas & Cabahug (2017)	Qualitative
	Dalanon & Matsuka (2017)	Quantitative
	Allam & Martin (2020)	Qualitative
	Gale (2017)	Qualitative
	Mar et al. (2017)	Quantitative
Stakeholders Engagement	Mangonon (2022)	Quantitative
	Roxas et al. (2019)	Quantitative
	Presente (2021)	Quantitative
	Sagnep and Valencia (2022)	Mixed method
	Tambogon & Tabuga (2017)	Qualitative
	Lago (2015)	Quantitative
	Undalok (2015)	Quantitative
	Muega (2016)	Mixed method
Learning Environment	Niro & Petilla (2019)	Quantitative
	Labrague (2018)	Quantitative
	De Jesus (2018)	Mixed method
	Acdal (2019)	Quantitative
	Zerrudo (2017)	Mixed method
	Wong & Daroja (2015)	Document Review
	Sumayang et al. (2022)	Scoping review
	Rosales et al. (2022)	Quantitative
	Cerbo (2017)	Mixed method
	Dotimas (2023)	Quantitative
Instruction	Formoso (2019)	Qualitative
	Ciocon (2022)	Quantitative
	Roxas et al. (2019)	Quantitative
	Paruginog & Fastidio (2017)	Quantitative
	Cahapay (2022)	Quantitative
	Barrientos (2022)	Quantitative
	Lopres et al. (2023)	Quantitative
	Abrazado & Dalonos (2021)	Qualitative
	Balmeo et al. (2014)	Mixed method
	Campado et al. (2023)	Qualitative
	Mendoza (2022)	Qualitative
	Vicente (2022)	Qualitative
	Manguilimotan, 2022	Mixed method

RQ1: Challenges to Special Education in the Philippines

Challenges on Instruction. A total of 14 studies were considered by the researcher as containing substantive discussion regarding instructional issues in dealing with learners with special education needs. Two studies are specifically dedicated on the challenges of instructional supervisors (Formoso, 2019; Ciocon, 2022); one study zeroed in on lack of instructional materials (Roxas et al., 2019), three studies stood out on the issue of instructional strategies (Paruginog & Fastidio, 2017; Cahapay, 2022; Barrientos, 2022; Lopres et al., 2023) while five studies have centered on technological challenges in instruction (Abrazado & Dalonos, 2021; Balmeo et al., 2014; Campado et al., 2023; Manguilimotan, 2022; Mendoza, 2022; Vicente, 2022).

The study of Formoso (2019) distinctively captured the perspectives of instructional supervisors and articulated their evolving role in providing instructional leadership to learners with special education needs. This qualitative study with study site in Pampanga acknowledged methodological limitations of supervision practices such as classroom observation, walk-throughs, and random visitation on top of facing challenges related to a lack of knowledge and training in SPED, constrained resources, and collaboration issues with regular teachers and parents. Taking a quantitative route, the study of Ciocon (2022) meanwhile advanced the importance of professional characteristics of school heads (i.e., educational attainment, plantilla position, length of service as school head, and length of service in a school with SPED program) in influencing success in special education program delivery.

Meanwhile, the study of Roxas et al. (2019) in the Division of Aurora has also covered the challenge of having lack of instructional materials. Through a quantitative assessment, respondents of said study have graded the dimension of instructional materials as “sometimes observed,” indicative of inconsistent access to these materials in the context of special education.

Challenges in instruction have been dealt with through various instructional strategies such as the study of Parugnog & Fastidio (2017) which utilized 3H approach—Heads-on (mental), Hands-on (doing) and Hearts-on (interest/symbolic)—in teaching numbers to learners with exceptionalities specifically those with conditions of cerebral palsy, autism, hearing impairment, and suspected learning disability. The study of Lopres et al. (2023) focused on academic essay writing strategies through traffic light color, planning using informal outline, and framed paragraph strategies to overcome challenges on lack of time for instruction and inadequacy of strategies both on the part of students and teachers. Barrientos (2022) affirmed the use of teacher-made books to cater to the differentiated needs of learners with exceptionalities. The role of efficacy for inclusion in the conduct of strategies and intervention practices was meanwhile provided in the study of Cahapay (2022) which suggested that teachers with high efficacy for inclusion have greater likelihood to employing effective intervention practices.

This survey of literature also shows that discourse on inclusive education keeps abreast with the times as several local studies have centered concerns on the challenges brought about by technological changes. The study of Abrazado and Dalonos (2021) in Northern Mindanao has brought up challenges by educators of special education in dealing with the use of online technology at the height of the pandemic, showing feelings of frustration, empathy, and altruism. Insufficient training in technology integration in special education was also highlighted by Balmeo et al. (2014), Campado et al. (2023), and Vicente (2022). Manguilimotan (2022) and Mendoza (2022) meanwhile emphasized issues on Internet connectivity and parents’ satisfaction with online education.

Challenges on Diverse Learning Environment. The researcher has noted nine studies that touched on learning environment in two distinct learning spaces: in special education centers and in mainstream classrooms.

As for learning environments in SPED learning centers, two studies were found to be particularly relevant: Labrague (2018) and De Jesus (2018). The former showed issues on admission and accessibility of SPED learning centers in Catbalogan City, Samar with low turnout rate among learners with disabilities in the city because of distance to school, lack of special facilities, and other support deficits, potentially defeating the purpose of inclusive diverse learning environment. Similarly, the latter study evaluated special education centers in Bulacan through SWOT analysis and found “moderate support,” suggesting the imperative for funding and support.

In mainstreamed classrooms, Acdan's (2019) study showed that generally, teachers have high acceptance and accommodation of learners with special needs. However, all other studies reached consensus on Allan and Martin's (2020) pronouncement that placing learners with special needs in inclusive classrooms without proper support is insufficient. Zerrudo (2017) pounded on the inadequate support and resources while Wong and Daroja (2015) emphasized the uneven implementation of the special education program in various sites in the country. Sumayang et al. (2022) brought up the need for manageable class size, in the same way that Rosales et al. (2022) revealed that teachers "greatly encounter" behavioral problems and "encountered" cognitive development problems among learners. Teachers also feel exasperated due to demanding workload (Dotimas, 2023) in dealing with manic and overactive learners (Cerbo, 2017).

Challenges on Curriculum Development. Challenges devoted towards curriculum development in special education is not well-articulated in the literature. Reading through selected pieces, studies concerning inclusive education or special education in the Philippines have broadly touched upon curriculum development where only four studies stood out with sufficient focus on curriculum of inclusive education: Mangonon (2022), Roxas et al. (2019), Raguindin (2020), and Pawilen et al. (2018).

Both the studies of Manonon (2022) and Roxas et al. (2019) covered curriculum compliance through quantitative measures. Both studies have also indicated positive results where Manonon's (2022) study in Sarangani province expressed "high level of compliance" in curriculum compliance while Roxas et al.'s (2019) study in the Division of Aurora have rated an overall "positive implementation" of the curriculum. Raguindin's (2020) paper shared similar observation, noting that concepts on inclusive education are articulated in the K-12 curriculum. Meanwhile, Pawilen et al. (2018) contributed in the discourse by presenting a comprehensive curriculum development model specific to the Transition Program for special learners with intellectual and physical disabilities.

Challenges on Stakeholders Engagement. It always takes a community to raise a child. Especially in the context of learners with special education needs, education managers must link arms not only to teachers but to the learners' parents and the community. In this review, the researcher synthesized nine studies that touched on stakeholders' engagement with focus on collaboration with family, the community, and local government units.

The study of Mangonon (2022) in Sarangani Province, Roxas et al. (2019) in the Division of Aurora, Presente (2021), and Sagnep & Valencia (2022) all dealt substantially on how parental and familial support are necessary in the learning of learners with special education needs. Mangonon (2022) raised the challenge of parents lacking the necessary skills and financial resources to manage their children's behavior and facilitate learning. Roxas et al. (2019) brought up parental attitude, specifically those of parents who are still in denial with their children's disabilities. Sagnep and Valencia's (2022) study on the utilization of a 3-week home Parent-Assisted Learning Plan raised the challenge of the lack of formal sign language training of parents who serve as home learning facilitators. Presente (2021) meanwhile zeroed in on family limitations and minimal opportunities for family education and training similar to the work of Lago (2015) which asserted not only limited family training opportunities but also the communication gap in conveying relevant SPED policies to family members.

Tambogon & Tabuga (2017) asserted that inclusive education is a collaborative effort together with the community. Discourse with respect to community involvement meanwhile revolves around awareness and engagement (Undalok, 2015; Muega, 2016) as well as community baselining of children with special needs (Roxas et al., 2019). The study of Undalok

(2015) laid emphasis on the imperative to drumbeat advocacy work pertaining to hearing-impaired education programs and raise awareness, address societal perceptions, disseminate information, and foster collaboration for more inclusive educational practices. This is akin to Muega's (2016) work which explored knowledge and involvement of stakeholders in inclusive education. Roxas et al. (2019) enriched this observation, reporting a "moderate level of engagement" from the community, especially with respect to ongoing efforts to identify pupils with exceptionalities at the community level.

One study has exceptionally studied engagement with government and non-government agencies in extracting funding for special education projects catering learners with special education needs. Niro and Petilla (2019) pounded on the necessity for concerted efforts to address serious financial constraints but have also brought to the fore challenges in regular coordination with local government officials and other stakeholders.

Challenges on Training and Professional Development. The condition where most learners with special needs are taught by general education teachers raises questions as to the capacity-building exercises that they are undertaking to bridge knowledge and competencies required in handling SPED learners. Four studies were synthesized as having sufficient focus on the area of training in inclusive and special education. Empirical studies identified expressed challenges on teachers' qualifications (Alfane, 2020), pre-service trainings (Aranan & Cabahug, 2017), and teachers' sense of efficacy (Dalanun & Matsuka, 2017; Allam & Martin, 2020).

The study of Alfane (2020) in Legazpi City addressed the lack of baseline information and revealed insights into the qualifications and demographics of SPED teachers in the area, showing a dearth of teachers with master's degrees and TESDA NC II qualifications. Interestingly, the study also emphasized that teaching in Special Education is not attractive to male teachers, and half of the teachers receive below the standard starting salary.

In Northern Mindanao, the work of Aranas and Cabahug (2017) focused on the critical issue of preparing non-special education elementary school teachers for inclusive education. The study revealed a limited emphasis on inclusion competencies in the syllabi. Gaps identified in understanding exceptionality, collaboration, inclusive instructional strategies, and assessment call for a more comprehensive and integrated approach to teacher preparation.

Meanwhile, the studies of Dalanon & Matsuka (2017), Allam & Martin (2020), and Mar et al. (2017) foregrounded teachers' sense of efficacy (TSE) in inclusion classes but showed contesting results. On one hand, the study of Dalanon & Matsuka (2017) documented a positive sense of efficacy despite acknowledged limitations in professional preparation. On the other hand, the study of Allam & Martin (2020) and Mar et al. (2017) demonstrated a sense of inadequacy, stress in terms of control and support, and even attrition due to desire for professional growth (Gale, 2017) hence the urgent need for targeted training and resource allocation to enhance teacher preparedness.

RQ 2: Research Gaps

Looking through the selected studies, the researcher has identified the following research gaps related to current discussions in local research about special education:

- (1) Absence of discourse on Assessment and Reporting. If the results of this review are to be analyzed vis-à-vis dimensions under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, all dimensions are covered in the existing literature except for Assessment and Reporting. While there may be a few studies that have broadly glossed over

assessment and reporting especially in studies related to individualized education planning, the researcher notes that the lack of empirical studies focused on this aspect is concerning and warrants further investigation.

- (2) Among the themes identified in this review, curriculum development posed the least number of available studies, making it accurate to say that curriculum management in inclusive and special education remains an underexplored discourse in local literature. Existing discourse is also focused on the level of curriculum compliance evaluation, overlooking the aspect of curriculum planning and enhancement.
- (3) The principles of “diversity of learners” and conducive learning environment are mentioned in most of the studies reviewed. It is therefore surprising that there remains a lack of studies that is dedicated towards these aspects especially as learners with special education needs are already integrated in mainstream schools.
- (4) Parent-teacher collaboration has been brought up as a necessary component of any special education program. But as the literature has pointed out, there is a lack of training to parents and families of learners. And assuming that in rare instances where there are, these family trainings are left unevaluated or not scaled up as research undertaking in itself as evidenced by the absence of evaluation studies on family trainings and parental SPED orientations.
- (5) The training needs of general education teachers on special education is well-pronounced in the survey of literature. But, as Aranas and Cabahug (2017) pointed out, there is a need for more comprehensive and integrated approach to teacher preparation
- (6) The survey of literature shows the most often employed research design is quantitative research. While these quantitative methods come from theoretically-informed and empirically-verifiable set of indicators, just by keeping tabs on certain parameters have the tendency to lose sight of other on addressing the experiential needs of educators and their learners with special education needs.

RQ 3: RECOMMENDATIONS

The articulation of research gaps allows us to explore various research prospects for further investigation including:

- (1) Focused studies on inclusive assessment and reporting tools;
- (2) Focused studies on curriculum planning and development addressed towards the differentiated needs of learners with special education needs;
- (3) Studies devoted towards mainstreamed learning environments of learners;
- (4) Evaluative studies on parental or family SPED trainings;
- (5) More literature on teacher preparation of general education teachers handling SPED learners;
- (6) The use of other methods in capturing specific challenges of special education in the country.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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